

Role of Acid Concentration on the Anodic Film Properties of Al and Al-Mn Alloy

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The effect of different concentrations of citric, tartaric, oxalic and sulphuric acids on the anodic film properties of Al and Al-Mn alloy has been investigated. The anodised specimens were exposed to the corrosive medium (HCl) and the corrosion rate was examined using Mylius thermometric method, weight-loss technique and hydrogen evolution measurements. The properties of the anodic film formed in the acids have been discussed in the light of their resistance to corrosion.

FARADAY assumed that passivation of the metal is caused by the formation of a thin, usually oxide film on the surface of the metal which ceases to interact with the surrounding medium and is thus protected from dissolving¹. Miyate and Setoh^{2,3} found that films formed in certain acids like sulphuric and oxalic consist of a thin, inner, compact barrier layer which thickens by ionic movement and a thick outer porous layer formed by conversion of the barrier layer. The barrier layer thickness is controlled by the applied voltage, temperature and concentration. Trillat and Tertian⁴ claimed that films formed in 2.0 M sulphuric acid yield an outer layer containing a mixture of crystalline γ - Al_2O_3 and boehmite α - $\text{AlO}(\text{OH})$ whereas the inner layer is amorphous Al_2O_3 . Water incorporated into the film slowly converts the amorphous oxide to monohydrate.

Kape⁵ presented voltage-time curves at constant current density for a variety of acids. Strong anodising acids such as sulphuric and sulphonic work at nearly constant voltage at room temperature and produce nearly clear films of natural colour. Weak anodising acids like tartaric, malonic and sulphosalicylic tend to have a rising voltage-time curve and produce dark films. Murphy and Michelson⁶ thought that the ability to anodise aluminium in dibasic or tribasic acids is related to the strength or extent of adsorption at the anodic film surface as well as to the concentration of anions and protons in solution. It is found that divalent anions adsorb much better than the monovalent ones. Lamb⁷ used electron probe microanalysis to study the behaviour of large intermetallic particles upon subsequent anodising in oxalic acid.

In the present work, the four acids, citric and tartaric (which were found to give anodic films of the barrier type), oxalic and sulphuric acids (which gave anodic films of the porous type)⁸ were selected to investigate the effect of their concentrations on the anodic film properties.

Experimental

The specimens of Al and Al-Mn alloy sheets (1.0×10.0 cm) were degreased in a mixture of Na_2CO_3 and Na_3PO_4 at 85° for 5.0 min, then washed with distilled water followed by dipping in pickling solution (10% HCl, v/v)⁹ for 1 min and washed in double-distilled water. The composition of Al and Al-Mn samples was respectively 99.7% Al (0.1 Mn, 0.1 Fe and 0.1% Si) and 97.8% Al in Al-Mn (2.0 Mn, 0.1 Si and 0.1% Fe). Anodisation of Al and Al-Mn was carried out in a cell at 30° using a copper sheet (10×20 cm) as cathode and the anodising solution (250 ml). The effect of each of the acids, viz. oxalic, citric, tartaric and sulphonic of concentrations viz. 1.0, 0.75, 0.50, 0.25 and 0.10 M on the anodisation process was investigated at 30° with a current density of 1.0 A dm^{-2} for a period of 60 min. The anodised specimens ($1.0 \times 5.0 \times 0.1$ cm) were dipped in 3.0 N HCl (30 ml) at 30° the placed in Mylius apparatus. The rise of temperature by time was measured. The value of $\Delta T_m/t$ defined as the reaction number (R.N.) (where ΔT_m is the maximum rise in temperature and t the time required for the temperature to reach T_m) was taken as a measure of the corrosion rate of the anodised specimens. The relative decrease in the reaction number (A) is given by, $A = (\text{R.N.} - \text{R.N.}') / \text{R.N.} \times 100$, where R.N. and R.N.' are the reaction numbers of non-anodised and anodised specimens respectively.

Weight-loss and hydrogen evolution measurements: The samples ($0.10 \times 1.0 \times 1.7$ cm) after being anodised, washed, dried and weighed, were immersed in 3.0 N HCl (250 ml). The volume of hydrogen gas evolved during corrosion was collected. After a time interval of 30 min, the corroding metal sample was withdrawn, washed, dried and weighed. The loss in weight was determined and the corrosion rate calculated according to the equation, $K = (W \times 10^3) / (4 \times t)$, where K is the rate of corrosion in

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($\text{g m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$), W the weight loss of the corroding specimen after a time period t . The volume of the H_2 gas collected during corrosion was corrected at the conditions of S.T.P. The amount of Al equivalent to the evolved hydrogen is calculated as

$$X = \frac{V \times 27 \times 2}{22414 \times 3}$$

where X is the weight of dissolved Al which is equivalent to the evolved H_2 (V) at S.T.P., 27 is the atomic weight of Al and $2/3$ is a factor to convert the moles of hydrogen and aluminium into equivalents. Thus the rate of corrosion ($\text{g m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$) is given by

$$X/t.S = (0.000803 \times V)/(0.5 \times 0.00040) = 4.015 V$$

where t is time (0.5 h in this work) and S is the surface area (4.0 cm^2).

Results and Discussion

The anodised specimens of Al and Al-Mn alloy were treated in Mylius apparatus containing 3.0 N HCl (30 ml). Fig. 1 presents the ΔT vs t curves for the anodised Al in different concentrations of citric acid (0.1–1.0 M) as a representative result. It is obvious that the corrosion resistance increases with increasing the acid concentration up to 0.5 M, followed by a decrease as the concentration increases.

Fig. 1. Plots of ΔT vs t for Al anodised in different concentrations of citric acid: (1) 0.10, (2) 0.25, (3) 0.50, (4) 0.75 and (5) 1.0 M.

The anodised Al-Mn in tartaric acid behaved similar to that in citric acid while Al metal does not obey any linear relationship. This behaviour of

the anodic film formed in citric and tartaric acids is most probably due to the formation of anodic film of the barrier type¹⁰⁻¹⁵. The corrosion resistance of the anodic film formed in oxalic and sulphuric acids was found to decrease with the increase in the acid concentration used for anodisation, a behaviour which is ascribed to the different contributions of the anodic dissolution and the anodic oxide formation reactions¹⁶.

In dilute solutions of oxalic and sulphuric acids, the predominating anodic reaction seems to be the oxide film formation. By increasing the acid concentration, the participation of the dissolution reaction in the anodic process increased, thereby leading to less corrosion resisting anodic films. It seems that the anodic film thickness and in turn its protecting property is inversely proportional to the anodising acid concentration. It is reported¹⁷ that higher the concentration of the anions in solution, the easier is the anodic dissolution of the metals and the higher the passivation potential. The anodisation of Al and Al-Mn in oxalic and sulphuric acids led to the formation of porous anodic films. This fact makes the anodic dissolution of Al or Al-Mn quite an expectable phenomenon. The reaction number (R.N.) for the dissolution of the untreated and the treated Al and Al-Mn in the four acids of different concentrations along with the relative decrease in the reaction number (A) are tabulated in Table 1. The values of A could be considered as resulting from the effect of the formed anodic film on the corrosion rate of the anodised Al and Al-Mn specimens. This $A-C$ relationship illustrates the effect of acid concentration on the quality of the anodic film. In oxalic and sulphuric acids, the film resistance to corrosion decreased on increasing the concentration (Table 1). In citric and tartaric acids, the film resistance to corrosion increased first and then decreased with the further increase in the acid concentration. The case of Al anodised in tartaric acid is an exceptional one, where the corrosion resistance of the anodic film

TABLE 1—R. N. AND A VALUES FOR Al and Al-Mn ANODISED IN DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF DIFFERENT ACIDS (A VALUES IN PARENTHESIS)

Concn. M	H_2SO_4		Oxalic acid		Citric acid		Tartaric acid	
	Al	Al-Mn	Al	Al-Mn	Al	Al-Mn	Al	Al-Mn
0.00	2.63	7.56	2.63	7.56	2.63	7.56	2.63	7.56
0.10	0.48 (81.8)	1.07 (85.8)	0.44 (83.3)	1.13 (85.1)	0.46 (82.7)	3.24 (57.1)	0.57 (78.6)	1.47 (80.6)
0.25	0.52 (80.5)	1.12 (85.2)	0.53 (80.0)	1.40 (84.1)	0.34 (87.1)	1.67 (77.9)	0.73 (72.3)	1.17 (84.5)
0.50	0.60 (77.5)	1.23 (83.7)	0.60 (77.3)	1.21 (84.0)	0.27 (89.9)	0.96 (87.3)	0.79 (70.3)	1.10 (85.4)
0.75	0.70 (73.7)	1.36 (81.9)	0.87 (67.1)	1.24 (83.6)	0.31 (88.2)	0.97 (87.1)	0.73 (72.3)	1.25 (83.4)
1.00	0.80 (69.9)	1.71 (77.4)	0.73 (72.5)	1.23 (83.7)	0.49 (81.7)	1.57 (79.2)	0.85 (68.0)	1.33 (82.3)

decreased all the time with the increase in tartaric acid concentration.

According to the new method of calculation suggested earlier by us¹⁸, the plots $\log \Delta T$ vs t (where $t = a + b \log \Delta T$) for the anodised Al specimen in different concentrations of H_2SO_4 are given in Fig. 2. Similar plots are obtained with the other acids. The values of a and b calculated from these figures are shown in Tables 2 and 3. The factor $1/a$ is the rate of temperature increase with time at the beginning of corrosion process

Fig. 2. Plots of $\log \Delta T$ vs t for Al anodised in different concentrations of sulphuric acid: (1) 0.10, (2) 0.25, (3) 0.50, (4) 0.75 and (5) 1.0 M.

while $1/b$ is a function of corrosion rate after depassivation. The $\log \Delta T$ vs t straight line plots show certain break at different values of $\log \Delta T$. In the case of anodisation in oxalic and sulphuric acids, the values of ΔT at which b changed were inversely proportional to the concentration of the acid. Anodisation in 0.1 M oxalic or sulphuric acids gave the most resisting anodic films on Al or Al-Mn. On increasing the acid concentration, ΔT of inflection decreased. In the case of Al-Mn anodised in oxalic acid, no considerable change in ΔT of inflection was noticed by varying the acid concentration. In general, it is observed that the b values above the inflection point is lower than below it, which may point out that the dissolving phase is quite different in each case. Below ΔT of inflection the dissolving phase is mainly the oxide film while above ΔT of inflection it is most likely that the active nonanodised surface is interacting with the 3.0 N HCl solution.

At the beginning of corrosion, the time needed for ΔT to attain one degree is a ($t = a + b \log \Delta T$). Hence, the relative decrease in corrosion rate at $\Delta T = 0.5^\circ$ is $A_{\Delta T=0.5^\circ} = (1 - a/a') \times 100$. At higher ΔT values and below the inflection point T^* , the $A_{\Delta T} < T^* = (1 - b/b') \times 100$ and over inflection point, $A_{\Delta T} > T^* = (1 - b/b'_2) \times 100$, where a and b are the constants in equation, $t = a + b \log \Delta T$ for the nonanodised Al or Al-Mn, a' , b'_1 and b'_2 are constants for the anodised Al and Al-Mn. Their values are reported in Tables 2 and 3 for the anodised and nonanodised Al and Al-Mn in oxalic and sulphuric acids of different concentrations. From these values, the relative decrease in the corrosion rates A_1 , A_2 and A_3 were calculated. The values of A_1 and A_3 were found to be much

TABLE 2—VALUES OF a , b AND RELATIVE DECREASE IN CORROSION RATE A OF Al AND Al-Mn ANODISED IN DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF H_2SO_4

	Concn. mol dm ⁻³	a_1	b_1	ΔT^*	b_2	A_1 %	A_2 %	A_3 %
Al	0.00	11.8	5.0	—	—	—	—	—
	0.10	97.5	14.5	50.0	8.5	87.9	65.5	41.2
	0.25	92.5	11.7	40.2	6.0	87.2	57.4	16.7
	0.50	82.5	10.5	39.4	6.0	85.7	52.4	16.7
	0.75	68.5	9.5	38.0	6.0	82.8	47.4	16.7
1.00	64.5	9.0	38.5	6.0	81.7	44.4	16.7	
Al-Mn	0.00	2.6	2.0	—	—	—	—	—
	0.10	36.5	16.7	48.0	7.5	92.9	88.0	73.3
	0.25	34.0	16.7	44.0	6.0	92.4	88.0	66.7
	0.50	32.0	16.7	40.0	4.6	91.9	88.0	55.5
	0.75	30.0	16.7	36.5	4.0	91.3	88.0	50.0
1.00	20.5	17.2	36.0	4.2	87.3	88.4	52.4	

TABLE 3—VALUES OF a , b AND RELATIVE DECREASE IN CORROSION RATE A OF Al AND Al-Mn ANODISED IN DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF OXALIC ACID

	Concn. mol dm ⁻³	a_1	b_1	ΔT^*	b_2	A_1 %	A_2 %	A_3 %
Al	0.00	11.8	5.0	—	—	—	—	—
	0.10	88.5	28.5	45.0	12.0	86.7	82.5	58.3
	0.25	81.0	22.5	40.5	9.0	85.4	77.8	44.4
	0.50	74.0	14.5	39.6	7.5	84.1	65.5	39.3
	1.00	68.5	13.0	37.0	6.5	69.4	86.8	33.1
Al-Mn	0.00	2.6	4.0	—	—	—	—	—
	0.10	26.5	26.0	39.5	7.0	90.2	92.31	71.4
	0.25	26.0	25.0	40.5	7.0	90.0	92.0	71.4
	0.50	25.5	25.0	40.5	7.0	89.8	92.0	71.4
	1.00	25.0	24.0	39.0	7.0	89.2	91.6	71.4

higher than A_2 , which indicates that at $\Delta T > \Delta T^*$, it is more probable that the active metal surface is dissolving. At $\Delta T < \Delta T^*$, the oxide film is interacting with the 3.0 N HCl solution with lower rate than the metal itself.

Moreover, the corrosion rate of the anodised Al and Al-Mn was investigated by other two methods: the weight-loss and the hydrogen evolution (vide experimental). The data of the corrosion rate by the two methods and the effect of the anodising acid concentration on the corrosion rate are presented in Figs. 3 and 4 for anodised Al and Al-Mn in oxalic and sulphuric acids respectively

Fig. 3. Effect of anodising acid concentration on: (a) corrosion rate of Al and (b) relative decrease in corrosion rate of Al.

Fig. 4. Effect of anodising acid concentration on: (a) corrosion rate of Al-Mn, and (b) relative decrease in corrosion rate of Al-Mn.

as a representative case. The results indicate that the corrosion rate of the anodised specimens was always lower than that for the nonanodised. The increase in the anodising acid concentration was accompanied by a relative decrease in the corrosion resistance of the anodised specimens. The values of the relative increase in corrosion resistance A_w calculated from the weight-loss data are shown in Figs. 3 and 4. These values were found to be lower than A_1 and A_2 but close to values of A_3 (Tables 2 and 3). This is quite explainable on the basis of the incubation period phenomenon. The determination of A from $\Delta T-t$ relations is restricted to each stage of dissolution A_1 , A_2 and A_3 . In the weight-loss method, the values of A cover the first and further stages of dissolution.

The values of A_H calculated from the hydrogen evolution data are much higher than those estimated from the weight-loss method, especially in case of anodisation in sulphuric and oxalic acids. This is attributed to the quantity of the metal oxidised to Al_2O_3 . The dissolution of Al_2O_3 in HCl takes place without hydrogen evolution,

Thus, greater the anodic film formation, the greater will be the difference between the values of the

corrosion rate calculated from both the mentioned methods. On the other hand, for the anodised specimens in citric acids, A_H is close to that calculated from the weight-loss data. This may be due to the formation of a barrier type film during the anodisation which made further growth of the oxide very difficult.

Finally, the difference between the loss in weight (ΔW) and the equivalent amount of Al corresponding to the hydrogen volume (V_H) may thus be regarded as a function of the quantity of the metal oxidised to Al_2O_3 on the surface.

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